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Bridging science and privacy: Health data governance in the legal contexts of the EU and China

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Abstract

This paper presents a comparative study of health data governance legal frameworks in the context of digital health technologies between the European Union (EU) and China, focusing on the assisted living sector. As healthcare systems undergo digital transformation, the widespread use of advanced ICT has led to extensive health data collection, raising privacy concerns. The paper examines the legal responses in the EU and China, identifying gaps and contradictions in their regulatory approaches, and provides recommendations on how existing laws should evolve to address these challenges effectively.

Health data processing in the age of digital health

The core content of this paper is a comparative study of the legal frameworks for health data protection in the context of digital health technologies between the European Union (EU) and China, with a focus on the assisted living sector.

Our healthcare systems are undergoing a wave of digital transformation characterized by the widespread application of information and communication technologies (ICT) in various health and care settings. Advanced digital technologies such as artificial intelligence, big data analytics, wearable devices, health monitoring sensors, mobile applications, and robotics are increasingly permeating the healthcare sector (World Health Organization, 2018). With the progress of ICT, healthcare services are extending beyond hospitals into private residences. For example, Ambient Assisted Living (AAL) technologies promise to enable elderly individuals to live more independently in their own homes, reducing their reliance on caregivers (Climent-Pérez et al., 2020).

The extensive use of ICT in healthcare has led to an unprecedented scale of health data collection and processing, with vast amounts of health data being stored in electronic health records and other platforms. Assistive technologies, often in the form of wearable devices and sensors, may pose privacy threats as they capture the user's health and well-being status by collecting large amounts of data, such as vital signs, daily activities, and even environmental data. The World Health Organization (WHO) has noted that the proliferation of wearable technologies, sensors, mobile health applications, social media, and genomic data collected through sequencing has significantly expanded the scope of health data collected (World Health Organization, 2021).

Health data processing in the age of digital health

In response to this situation, countries have enacted laws to strengthen data protection in the digital health transformation. For example, the EU has passed multiple data protection laws, including the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Similarly, China enacted its first standalone data protection law, the Personal Information Protection Law, in 2021, which is expected to have a significant impact on technology and data processing. In an era of unprecedented health data processing, it is crucial to examine the impact of data protection and the extent to which existing laws can address new challenges.

Conclusions

The paper seeks to delineate the complex legal framework applicable to digital health technologies in the context of health data processing. It presents the legal regulation of health data in the EU and China, exploring similarities and differences between the two. The paper systematically presents the legal content according to the established hierarchy of legal sources, aiming to identify gaps and contradictions in the laws. While the research primarily focuses on traditional,

positivist legal analysis, it also offers recommendations on how the law should act where appropriate.

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